

ARCHITECTURE FOR AI-CHAT-ASSISTANTS IN ACADEMIA – TRUSTWORTHY THROUGH AN ALGORITHMIC FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

The EU's "Trustworthy AI" requirements emphasize high-quality data, legal compliance in data processing and storage, robust system control, and ensuring AI serves the well-being of users. Integrating AI-driven chat assistants in academia must adhere to these trust principles from the outset. This can be achieved through a framework that harmonizes algorithmic and generative intelligence to optimize both data trustworthiness and conversational quality.

At the core of the proposed architecture is the operation control component, orchestrating the entire system by ensuring high-quality data retrieval, enforcing compliance through guardians, and refining response processing to optimize AI-generated outputs—all within a user-centric interface that enhances effective interaction. Generative AI is only selectively used where necessary, such as for creative tasks like analyzing or generating text, while the core processes remain anchored in a transparent, rule-based algorithmic framework.

This article presents a blueprint for an architecture and which components are required in the interaction between algorithmic and generative intelligence, suggests names for these components, and proposes what specific tasks the individual modules of these components could be assigned. For instance, prompts are constructed by the algorithmic prompt composer, data is precisely gathered by the quality data retriever through the document vector fetcher, and outputs are seamlessly routed via the response data splitter.

The interplay of the architecture components results in a rule-based Retrieval-Augmented Generation (rRAG) framework that serves as a structured approach for embedding trust from the outset into AI systems. By ensuring a seamless interaction between algorithmic processes and generative AI, the proposed architecture reinforces "trust-driven AI" by structuring data retrieval and processing, ensuring hallucination-free data handling and trustworthy outputs. The architecture is not merely theoretical but has already been largely implemented and is actively used within the German project SMARTA (Student Motivation and Reflective Training AI-Assistants).

Keywords: AI, chatbots, assistants, architecture, trust, AI act, algorithm, academia, algorithmic prompt composer, qualified data retriever, SMARTA, trust-driven AI, Higher education.

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1 INTRODUCTION

A review of recent literature suggests that the transformation of higher education through Artificial Intelligence (AI) and AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants is reshaping student support, teaching practices, and administrative processes [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. These systems, for example, those based on GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) models, personalize learning, automate feedback, and assist with academic tasks [6], [7]. But their growing influence raises concerns about reliability, particularly the phenomenon of AI hallucination—when models generate misleading or false content [8], [9], delivered with a deceptive sense of confidence. Such errors threaten academic integrity and demand critical engagement with AI outputs [10], [11].

Defining the quality of data input and controlling the output are crucial for the reliability of AI systems. Key challenges include ensuring data accuracy, completeness, consistency, and uniformity [12], [13].

GPT-based chatbot integrations, esp. into higher-education systems, must minimize low-quality responses and try to achieve this by several distinct architectural patterns: Farah et al. [14] advocate a modular, system-agnostic design that separates functions into an interface engine, knowledge engine, interaction engine, and learning engine; Wang et al. [15] and Farah et al. [16] detail web application and Learn-Management-Systems (LMS) integrations that support context-aware responses and conversational memory. Standalone systems appear in Chen et al. [17] and Nayak et al. [18], with the latter implementing a custom Entity Recognition tool to enforce GDPR-compliant data handling.

Most of the architectures focus on Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), which offers a technical solution by integrating verified external knowledge into AI responses, thereby reducing hallucination and enhancing factual accuracy [19], [20]. Studies have shown that RAG can significantly improve accuracy and reduce fabrications in various applications, including academic virtual assistants and educational chatbots [21]. However, RAG is not infallible and can still be misled by contradictory prompts [22] or in cases where faulty external data sources were selected.

Some authors stress the need for communication with external databases, for example with the Model Context Protocol, which enables large language models to communicate with constraint programming systems to enhance formal reasoning capabilities [23]. This integration aligns with the vision of cognitive databases, which incorporate AI functionalities into relational databases to enable complex semantic queries and inductive reasoning [24].

For this reason, a blueprint for a framework is suggested, that balances algorithmic intelligence and generative intelligence to optimize both trustworthy data and conversational quality—with clear guardrails. One possibility to improve trustworthiness could be a rule-based RAG (rRAG), where algorithmic rules decide about the input and check the output of each AI-interaction.

2 RULE-BASED AND GENERATIVE INTELLIGENCE

2.1 Rigid, Learning, and Generative AI in Context

AI refers to systems that take over tasks that usually require human thinking – such as making decisions or creating content. Both traditional rule-based approaches and modern data-based machine learning are likely to continue playing an important role in higher education system. [5]

1. **Rigid algorithmic intelligence** consists of rule-based processes defined by humans. These are transparent and can be used without relying on data – for example, to calculate a final grade exactly according to examination regulations, for each student.
2. **Learning algorithmic intelligence** also follows rules defined by humans. However, the human has determined that these rules should adapt based on current data – for example, to analyse which rooms were frequently used for specific group topics in the past, and to suggest suitable room assignments accordingly.
3. **Generative intelligence**, on the other hand, is based on machine-learned patterns from training data and can, for example, generate a personalized learning chat on the topic of "Economy" – adapted to the student's language proficiency. This learning chat can
 - a. be based on the general training data of the generative intelligence, such as Wikipedia, or
 - b. it can be grounded in the teaching material of the university. To ground

- i. the generative intelligence can independently search through all course materials of the university (Retrieval-Augmented Generation/RAG),
- ii. or rules can be defined that precisely specify which available databases or course documents should be used for which learning text generation (rule-based Retrieval-Augmented Generation/rRAG).

Depending on the problem in higher education, the right type of AI must be chosen. For instance, algorithmic intelligence cannot create a PowerPoint slide, and generative intelligence should not creatively calculate a student's final grade. Only the combination of algorithmic and generative intelligence can lead to trustworthy systems – for example, when a request refers to an examination regulation, the algorithm decides which regulation applies, provides it to the generative AI as a document, and then the generative AI responds based on the correct regulation. The strength of rule-based transparency is then combined with the creative power of generative AI. The described framework suggests the concept of rRAG, which will be described in the following.

2.2 Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) vs. Rule-Based RAG

Large language models (LLM) are known for their ability to generate fluent text, but they often suffer from hallucination—producing factually incorrect or unverifiable statements. This presents a serious challenge in higher education, where accuracy, transparency, and trust are essential. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) addresses this issue by combining language models with external knowledge sources: relevant documents are retrieved, typically via vector search, and used to ground the model's output in real information. However, standard RAG systems rely on unstructured data and open-ended retrieval, which can limit transparency and control. In open RAG, the AI system decides which documents and data are used, which is considered risky.

In contrast, the decision about which document/data should be used could be predefined by human-created rules to meet the specific demands of academic environments. Therefore, a rule-based RAG (rRAG) is introduced here: a structured variant that replaces open search with predefined logic, drawing context from trusted sources such as databases, session variables, or role-based access. Optional semantic enrichment within scoped documents remains possible, but always under institutional control. This approach enables AI systems to deliver personalized, reliable, and explainable support—ideal for student advising, campus automation, and learning assistance.

3 rRAG-ARCHITECTURE COMPONENTS

The proposed rRAG-architecture is organized into clearly defined categories, each serving a specific role within the overall system design. Each category contains individual modules. A module serves both as a conceptual unit for understanding system functionality and, in implementation, as code pages or sets of code lines grouped by function. Categories are:

At the core of the architecture lies Operation Control—the central orchestrating layer. It relies on the Qualified Data Retrieval (QDR) for data acquisition and the Response Data Splitter (RDS) to manage dual output channels: one for user-facing communication and another for internal exchange between the LLM and the rRAG-system itself. This dual-channel structure is assumed to be essential for enabling intelligent, traceable, and adaptive system behavior.

The Guardians category is responsible for ensuring rule-compliant and controlled system use. For example, the Adaptive Task Dispatcher (ATD) ensures that only tasks relevant to the student's study program and current situation are made available. The Access & Quota Controller (AQC) monitors access token quotas, while the Critical Content Guard (CCG) and the Compliance & Policy Checker (CPC) ensure that outputs remain appropriate and legally safe.

The Chat Interface category governs how users interact with the system. The Frontend Chat Assistants (FCA) ensure a user-friendly and personalized interface—such as selecting a suitable assistant like Reflection-Robyn, Motivation-Alix or Dr. Melly for learning support.

The Operation Control category orchestrates the logical flow and modular activation. The Algorithmic Prompt Composer (APC) plays a central role by generating context-sensitive prompts based on structured data. Additionally, Organisational Admin Access (OAA) allows institutions to define which institutional data and prompt structures are to be used.

The Data Retrieval category is one of the most extensive. It includes the Qualified Data Retriever (QDR) and its submodules to fetch institutional data, retrieve student-specific data, focuses on course data and define the task context. All these rely on the QDR Data Source Manager (DSM), which pulls information from internal (DAin) and external (DAex) sources. External data access is governed by the QDR Exchange Protocol (QDR-EP), for example by using a customized one-way Model Context Protocol (MCP).

Figure 1. rRAG-Architecture in SMARTA

The Vector Document Fetcher (VDF) integrates academic documents from the Vector Document Store (VDS) as well as associated prompts from the Vector Prompt Store (VPS), both of which are curated by the university administration or lecturers.

The Multimodal category determines how responses are created and delivered. The Multimodal Model Controller (MMC) selects the modality and model to be used (e.g., GPT-4), which depends on task and usage history. MMC can activate modules for text generation, image generation, or speech synthesis. Additionally, MMC roughly estimates the required tokens and the cost per model token, allowing it to show users the cost of their request—or even its ecological impact in CO₂-equivalents.

The AI-Service category covers the strictly defined interaction channel with the Large Language Model (LLM), which generates the actual response once a prompt has been fully constructed.

The Response Processing category ensures that the AI's output is parsed and relevant results are stored properly. The Response Data Splitter (RDS) separates visible dialogue from system metadata and the additional hidden data, which is actively demanded by the APC. This hidden data is given to the User Response Analyzer (URA) like the Sentiment Analysis Module (SAM) or the Quiz Evaluation Module (QEM), for algorithmic analysis and storage.

The Memory category manages both short- and long-term retention. Chat Dialogue Memory (CDM) handles session memory, while Short-Term Memory (STM) captures transient user insights, and Long-Term Memory (LTM) stores persistent learning data and outcomes.

Lastly, the Monitor category enables transparency and analytics. The Logging & Monitoring System (LoMo) records technical events, and the Anonymous Usage Tracker (AUT) ensures system and token usage can be monitored in compliance with privacy standards.

Based on the diagram, a simplified version of the interaction process can be described as follows: While the AI assistant is capable of initiating a chat, this scenario assumes the user starts the interaction. After the user initiates a chat request (Arrow 1 in Fig. 1), a chat begins with the activation of the chat assistant, which then triggers the Prompt Composer (Arrow 2) to request relevant data (Arrow 3). This data is provided by the Qualified Data Retriever (Arrow 6). The APC passes the completed prompt (Arrow 7) to the Large Language Model. The model's response is analyzed and partially stored internally (Arrow 8), while the rest—after a compliance check—is displayed to the user (Arrow 10). The response is also algorithmically analyzed and passed back to the Prompt Composer (Arrow 15), which then prepares the next dialogue step and prompt addition. The process repeats iteratively, with each prompt sent to the LLM for processing, followed by structured splitting, parsing, and evaluation.

4 EXAMPLE USE CASE: TIM'S LEARNING CHAT

4.1 Initial User Personalization

To understand the process and interaction between algorithmic and generative intelligence, let's look at an example. Tim, a student, clicks on "Next Lecture: Economy" in the campus management system. From his perspective, this starts a simple chat. In reality, the interaction is precisely orchestrated and managed through algorithmic processes.

As expected, Tim immediately receives information about the time and location of the next lecture: "Hi Tim, the next Economy lecture is this afternoon. It is about inflation. Don't forget to bring a calculator. P.S.: Did you know that inflation affects car sales?"

The personalized follow-up mentioning "inflation" and "car sales" can be explained as follows:

At the beginning of the conversation, before the "Hi Tim", algorithms collect relevant information to generate a suitable AI prompt. Before the first chat-opening, key data about the student and the topic and the university is used to personalize the dialogue.

Based on algorithmically collected data, the rRAG-System identifies Tim clearly as a 30-year-old part-time master's student in Business Administration at a German University of Applied Sciences—and not as a 20-year-old female biology student. This distinction is crucial, as different users respond to different forms of motivation, and the initial prompt must be adapted accordingly. The rRAG-System knows and uses for crafting the prompt, that Tim is currently in his second semester (out of six), which ends in four weeks with exams. The system remembers that Tim has used the chatbot frequently in the past, most recently yesterday, and that he once mentioned his hobby—spending time with his dog, Tappy—as well as his job as a sales assistant at a car dealership.

The system also knows that Tim is currently enrolled in three lectures. One of them is Economics, which he recently described as boring. It knows that the next lecture is this afternoon, and that materials on "inflation" have already been uploaded to the course archive. According to the official module handbook, this topic is part of the main theme "Macroeconomic Indicators." From the official course script, it also knows that inflation is one of the four key goals in the so-called "magic square" of economic policy, and that a recommended book is authored by John Maynard Keynes.

Finally, the system remembers that Tim's math performance in the first semester was below average. It is also aware that in past conversations, his sentiment was often negative, and that he struggles with motivation and procrastination. Additionally, the system knows that Tim prefers to hear content in easy

German with a youthful tone and short sentences, rather than reading long theoretical texts in academic English.

With this context, the Algorithmic Prompt Composer (APC) is able to create a personalized system prompt, used for the AI and therefore to guide the conversation from the beginning in a way that is adapted to Tim's academic situation, motivation, and learning preferences.

4.2 System Orchestration Step-by-Step

4.2.1 Initial System Prompt

To determine which assistants or features Tim can use, the Adaptive Task Dispatcher (ATD) from the Guardians category takes over. In this case, ATD grants Tim access to the economics coaching assistant because he is currently enrolled in the course and the exam is just four weeks away.

To ensure that Tim's system usage stays within defined limits, the Access & Quota Controller (AQC), part of the Guardians category, monitors availability. If sufficient quota remains, AQC authorizes the learning session to proceed.

To provide Tim with the appropriate conversational interface, the Frontend Chat Assistants (FCA) from the Chat Interface category handle the selection. In this case, 'Dr. Melly' is chosen for her specialization in learning support.

The prompt processed by the Large Language Model (LLM) consists of the initial system prompt, the subsequent user input, and the chatbot responses (assistant prompt) that follow.

To craft a well-targeted initial system-prompt that reflects Tim's situation, the Algorithmic Prompt Composer (APC) from Operation Control steps in. In this scenario, APC requests the Qualified Data Retriever (QDR) to gather relevant data, including information about the student, institution, task, and course. QDR uses the Data Source Manager (DSM) to gather information from internal databases, internal documents, or external databases.

- The Institutional Data Retriever (QDR-I) gathers essential information about the university and degree program, such as its status as a 'University of Applied Sciences,' its private ownership, its focus on business studies, its main campus in Berlin, and Tim's part-time enrollment in a small study group of 10 students.
- To gather student-specific data such as gender, age, engagement, and performance, the Student Data Retriever (QDR-S) is used. It collects Tim's gender, age range, recent activity on the learning platform, and relevant performance data like quiz results from his quiz chats.
- To retrieve course-related context, the Course Data Retriever (QDR-C) is activated. It looks up past and future appointments, learning objectives from the module handbook or topics from the schedule, the names of new uploaded materials, and whether an official learning script is available.
- To further refine the task context, the Task Context Requester (QDR-T) contributes. It defines that the planned chat dialogue is not primarily about motivation or reflection but about learning, and outlines a rough structure: an easy multiple-choice question, a short story about exponential growth, a guessing task, and a reflective discussion on "inflation and sales."
- To enrich and ground the prompt with an official document, the Vector Document Fetcher (VDF) from Data Retrieval is used. In this case, VDF finds an academic text linked to the course and stored in the university's Vector Document Store (VDS). Together with the document, a document-specific prompt from the Vector Prompt Store (VPS) is provided.
- If external data is needed, the Exchange Protocol (QDR-EP) attempts to retrieve it.

Using the data provided by QDR, the APC again takes over and constructs the prompt. The prompt is created by algorithmic intelligence in a structured, machine-friendly format, containing about ten pages of contextual information on the student, task, course, and institution. It also includes instructions for the LLM to respond in a machine-parsable format, including additional data such as "sentiment analysis of the user's answer."

The Multimodal Model Controller (MMC) specifies that the output should be in text format and that the GPT-4 model should be used. Then comes the black box moment: the initial system-prompt is sent to the LLM, which returns an answer within seconds, which is then added to the system-prompt as the assistant-prompt.

Final step before the user sees the chat reply: To ensure compliance and content safety, the Critical Content Guard (CCG) from the Guardians category checks whether legally problematic language was used. For example, it scans for keywords like “exam” and may trigger predefined messages such as a red alert: “Attention. Information is non-binding.”

After the preceding steps, Tim is shown the opening chat text: “Hi Tim, the next Economy lecture is this afternoon. It is about inflation. Don’t forget to bring a calculator. P.S.: Did you know that inflation affects car sales?”

Let’s assume Tim responds with “cool, tell me more.”, which will be added as user input to the initial system-prompt and the assistant prompt.

4.2.2 Preparation of the Next Dialog Line

The user input is added to the past conversation and analyzed algorithmically. First, the Compliance and Policy Checker (CPC) checks for any forbidden or problematic keywords in the user response. If found, the relevant predefined warnings are displayed.

APC now generates the next dialogue step by creating a prompt for the planned multiple-choice question. Again, this prompt uses context from Tim’s world and is adapted to his age, tone, his mathematical abilities and the official learning objectives. Again, it is algorithms that create the prompt and process it to the LLM.

Once the LLM generates the next chat interaction, RDS parses the last user-input. To separate user-facing content from backend data, the Response Data Splitter (RDS) from the Operation Control category is used. Example: Let’s assume that the LLM detects “cool” as a positive sentiment and later evaluates the answer to the multiple-choice question as correct with 4 of 10 points. This information becomes part of the prompt as a hidden instruction—it is not shown to the user but part of the LLM-answer and can algorithmically be parsed by the RDS. Therefore, the output is split into the next visible dialogue line and background data, such as sentiment analysis or answer evaluation. Latter is written by the User Response Analyzer (URA) into the corresponding database tables (Long Term Memory) or, if it’s unstructured insights like hobbies, into Short Term Memory. URA also writes directly measurable data like tokens used or dialogue duration into the Logging and Monitoring System (LoMo).

The conversation progresses smoothly, with APC and RDS playing central roles. If additional data is required, APC consults the QDR, prompting the QDR Data Manager to retrieve it. Algorithmic processing and control introduce minimal latency—typically just a few milliseconds per step.

5 ORGANISATIONAL ADMINISTRATIVE ACCESS AND EXTERNAL DATA

Data acquisition within the system is designed to prioritize internal sources, due to their reliability and manageability. Core student and course information is retrieved directly from the campus management system. Through the Orga-Admin-Access (OAA), it can be defined which chat assistants are available for students, lecturers, or administrative staff (Arrow A in Fig. 1), and which institutional data should be used, and how a prompt for a given task should be roughly structured (Arrow C). In addition, the administrator can upload documents that are vectorized and linked to a task along with a predefined prompt (Arrow B). The architecture proposes that the Vector Document Store runs on a dedicated university server to comply with GDPR requirements.

If no internal data is available, external data for one or more categories—task, student, institution, course, or documents—can be requested via the QDR Exchange Protocol. For example, the administrative person might manage course content through an external learning management system such as Moodle (Arrow D).

Accessing external data is more complex than accessing internal data. It is recommended to use the Model Context Protocol (MCP) for this purpose. The Model Context Protocol (MCP) is a standard that defines how tools can request information in a clear and structured way—especially when used with AI or between AI systems. In the proposed rRAG-system, MCP is used only to bring data into the rRAG from external systems—never the other way around. The part of rRAG called QDR-EP uses MCP to send specific requests, such as asking for a student’s current semester, to connected external systems like other campus management systems or learning platforms. These requests and responses follow a fixed structure so that both sides know what to expect. MCP helps rRAG communicate clearly with external tools while maintaining full control over what is asked and how the data is used.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Hallucinations—wether by machines or humans—are statements that sound plausible but are factually incorrect. Hallucinations pose a particular risk in academic settings, whether in teaching, learning, or administration. Human hallucination—such as incorrect or misleading statements by lecturers—is not uncommon, although its frequency is difficult to quantify. Nevertheless, expectations towards AI systems are significantly higher. In academic contexts, AI is expected not to hallucinate, but to provide consistently accurate and verifiable information—ideally exceeding human reliability in terms of factual correctness. Inaccurate content can undermine trust, mislead students, or result in flawed administrative decisions. Addressing this challenge requires systems that are not only creatively intelligent, but also rule-based, institutionally controlled, and GDPR-compliant, and guided by clear guardrails. In addition, they must be user-friendly and well accepted by both students and lecturers.

This paper presents a blueprint for a rule-based Retrieval-Augmented Generation (rRAG) architecture, seamlessly combining algorithmic and generative intelligence to fulfill the demands of trustworthy AI in higher education. Key components—such as the Algorithmic Prompt Composer (APC), the Qualified Data Retriever (QDR), and the Response Data Splitter (RDS)—work together to ensure that AI-supported interactions are data-driven and legally compliant. The architecture emphasizes institutional control and personalization, embedding these principles into each step of the system's operation. Rather than remaining a conceptual model, the blueprint has already been largely implemented in the German campus management extension “Student Motivation and Reflective Training AI-Assistants” (SMARTA).

The terminology and structure presented are intended to provide a conceptual foundation for the design of similar AI architectures in academic contexts—supporting universities in evolving from AI experimenters to AI professionals or even AI frontrunners [25], in order to remain or become competitive, and to watch, contribute to, or ultimately make things happen—rather than remain passive observers wondering what happened in the age of AI in academia.

APPENDIX: TABLE OF CATEGORIES AND MODULES

<i>Category</i>	<i>Module</i>	<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Colour</i>
Guardians	Adaptive Task Dispatcher	ATD	Red
Guardians	Access & Quota Controller	AQC	Red
Chat Interface	Frontend-Chat-Assistants	FCA	Green
Operation Control	Algorithmic Prompt Composer	APC	Light Blue
Data Retrieval	Qualified Data Retriever	QDR	Blue
Data Retrieval	Institution Data Retriever	QDR-I	Blue
Data Retrieval	Task Context Requester	QDR-T	Blue
Data Retrieval	Course Data Retriever	QDR-C	Blue
Data Retrieval	Student Data Retriever	QDR-S	Blue
Data Retrieval	QDR Data Source Manager	QDR-DSM	Blue
Multimodal	Multimodal Model Controller	MMC	Orange
Multimodal	Text Generation Demand	TGE	Orange
Multimodal	Image Generation Demand	IGE	Orange
Multimodal	Speech Synthesis Demand	SSE	Orange
AI-Service	Large Language Model	LLM	Yellow
Response Processing	Response Data Splitter	RDS	Cyan
Response Processing	Chat-Meta-Data	CMD	Cyan
Monitor	Logging & Monitoring System	LoMO	Black
Guardians	Critical Content Guard	CCG	Red
Guardians	Compliance & Policy Checker	CPC	Red
Response Processing	User Response Analyzer	URA	Cyan
Response Processing	Sentiment Analysis Module	SAM	Cyan
Response Processing	Quiz Evaluation Module	QEM	Cyan
Monitor	Anonymous Usage Tracker	AUT	Black
Memory	Chat Dialogue Memory	CDM	Dark Blue
Memory	Long-Term Memory	LTM	Dark Blue
Memory	Short-Term Memory	STM	Dark Blue
Operation Control	Organisational Admin Access	OAA	Light Blue
Data Source	Vector Document Store	VDS	Grey
Data Source	Vector Prompt Store	VPS	Grey
Data Retrieval	Vector Document Fetcher	VDF	Blue
Data Source	Internal Data	DAin	Grey
Data Retrieval	QDR Exchange Protocol	QDR-EP	Blue
Data Source	External Data	DAex	Grey

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